

A STUDY ON PERCEPTION OF REVERSE MORTGAGE IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BENGALURU CITY

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Abstract

Reverse Mortgage is a financial product offered by financial institutions to senior citizens in India. It was introduced in 2007 to provide senior citizen homeowners with the opportunity to continue living in their homes while receiving either a monthly or lump-sum payment from financial institutions. These payments can be used to support their livelihood and cover various expenses. However, despite its potential benefits, reverse mortgage has not gained significant popularity in the country. This paper aims to explore the perceptions of respondents regarding reverse mortgage, while also identifying the key barriers to its adoption and the potential prospects for its growth in India.

Keywords: Reverse Mortgage, Senior Citizen, Perception, Barriers, Prospects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reverse mortgage is a financial innovative product. It is a loan product designed for senior citizens that allows them to convert the equity in their self-acquired, self-occupied residential property into a steady income stream. Unlike traditional loans, where borrowers make periodic payments to the lender, in a reverse mortgage, the lender makes payments to the borrower either as a monthly annuity, lump-sum amount, or a line of credit. The borrower can live in the same home without having the burden of repayment of debt.

1. History of Reverse Mortgage

The first official reverse mortgage product was introduced in 1961 to assist a widow in staying in her house, and the idea was initially introduced in the United States in the early 1960s. As the concept gained popularity, the Federal Housing Administration (FHA) of the United States government launched the Home Equity Conversion Mortgage (HECM) program in 1989.

Since then, the market for reverse mortgages has grown all over the world, especially in aging nations like Canada, the UK, Australia, and Japan. Every nation has customized the reverse mortgage concept to fit its own legal and socioeconomic environment. For instance, reverse mortgages are frequently utilized in Australia to pay for elderly care as well as everyday expenses. Adoption has been slower in Japan, where there is a strong inheritance culture.

2. Reverse Mortgage in India

Under the direction of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), the National Housing Bank (NHB) formally launched the reverse mortgage program in India in 2007. The objective was to allow senior adults (60 years of age and older) to get a consistent income against their residential property's mortgage without having to sell or move out. Public sector banks and home finance firms, such as the State Bank of India, Punjab National Bank, and LIC home Finance, supported the product's launch. Monthly payouts were initially permitted under the system for a maximum of 15 years. But this short time frame was viewed as constrictive, particularly for those who lived longer than anticipated. In order to solve this, the NHB partnered with insurance companies to establish the Reverse Mortgage Loan-enabled Annuity (RMLeA). Through partnerships with life insurance companies, senior individuals could earn lifetime annuity payments under the RMLEA, providing them with more financial security.

In India, reverse mortgage acceptance has remained modest in spite of these improvements. The Hindu Business Line (2019) reports that there are still fewer than 1,000 active reverse mortgage accounts at the leading Indian banks. This poor uptake is caused by a number of issues, such as a lack of understanding, a cultural and emotional attachment to property, worries about inheritance, complicated legal processes, and mistrust of financial institutions. The number of elderly people in India is increasing as a result of a demographic shift. The percentage of older adults is gradually growing due to increased life expectancy and falling birth rates. The Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation's (MoSPI) Elderly in India 2021 report estimates that there are 138 million people in India who are 60 years of age or older, and that number is projected to rise to 194 million by 2031. Significant socioeconomic issues are brought about by this demographic shift, especially with regard to the well-being and financial independence of the elderly population. Indian culture has long placed a strong emphasis on family members taking care of the elderly. However, intergenerational assistance has decreased as a result of younger generations migrating for work, nuclear families becoming more prevalent, and growing urbanization. Even though many elderly people own priceless real estate, including homes, they sometimes don't make enough money to cover their daily expenses, medical bills, and other unforeseen costs. The need for creative financial solutions geared toward the senior population has arisen from this dilemma of being "asset-rich but cash-poor." The urban metropolis of Bengaluru, which is well-known for its educated populace and high rate of retiree property ownership, provides an appropriate context for researching reverse mortgage awareness, acceptance, and difficulties. Many elderly individuals in the city own substantial residential assets but may lack regular income post-retirement. Understanding their perception of reverse mortgage schemes can provide insights into both the product's limitations and its potential for future growth.

3. Working of Reverse Mortgage

A **reverse mortgage** is a unique loan product that enables senior citizens to convert the equity in their self-occupied residential property into a regular source of income, without

having to sell or vacate their home. Unlike traditional loans where borrowers repay the loan through EMIs, in a reverse mortgage, the **lender pays the borrower**, and **repayment is deferred** until the borrower dies, sells the house, or permanently moves out.

4. Eligibility Criteria

- a. The typical eligibility conditions in India include:
- b. The borrower should be a senior citizen aged 60 years or above and in case of joint owner with spouse aged 58 and above.
- c. The property must be self-acquired, self-occupied, and free from any encumbrance.
- d. The house should have a clear title in the borrower's name.
- e. The property must have a minimum residual life of 20 years or more.

5. Loan Disbursement Options

Once the property is mortgaged with a financial institution, the borrower can choose from the following disbursement methods based on their financial and personal commitments.

- a. Monthly/Quarterly/Annual Payments (Annuity)
- b. Lump-sum Payment (for medical emergencies or large expenses)
- c. Line of Credit (withdrawals as needed)
- d. Combination of all the above

In some enhanced schemes like the Reverse Mortgage Loan-enabled Annuity (RMLeA), the lender ties up with a life insurance company to provide lifetime annuity payments, which continue even beyond 15-20 years.

6. Valuation and Loan Amount

The loan amount is based on the market value of the property, borrower's age, and interest rates. Generally, banks offer 30% to 60% of the property's value the older the borrower the higher will be the eligible amount. Interest is accrued on the loan over time, but not repaid during the borrower's lifetime. The loan (principal + accrued interest) becomes repayable only upon the death of the last surviving borrower, Sale of the property or Permanent move-out from the property.

7. Settlement of the Loan

- a. After the borrower's death, the legal heirs have the option to repay the loan and reclaim the property.
- b. If they choose not to repay, the lender sells the property to recover the dues.
- c. Any surplus after loan recovery is returned to the heirs.
- d. If the sale value is less than the loan amount, the lender bears the loss, not the heirs (as it's a non-recourse loan).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Reverse mortgage, as a financial instrument for senior citizens, has garnered attention in Indian academic and policy circles over the past two decades. Several researchers have examined the feasibility, perception, and effectiveness of reverse mortgage loans (RMLs) in addressing the financial needs of the ageing population in India.

Sarita Gupta and Sanjay Kumar (2017) explored the correlation between interest in reverse mortgages and knowledge about the product. Their analysis, which used chi-square and correlation methods, found no statistically significant relationship between the two. They concluded that lack of awareness is not the only barrier hindering the growth of the reverse mortgage market in India.

Swarn Chatterjee (2016) highlighted that only a small percentage of homeowners opt for reverse mortgages, with the uptake being particularly low among borrowers under the age of 50. The study revealed that reverse mortgages are more common among affluent or risk-averse individuals, while those with long-term care insurance are less likely to use them.

Daptardar and Dasgupta (2014) emphasized the growing importance of reverse mortgages in India, given the demographic shift marked by an ageing population. They pointed out that for many older Indian households, their home represents the most significant asset. Their study analyzed the reverse mortgage market from both demand and supply perspectives to determine whether such schemes can effectively meet retirees' financial needs.

Kang (2010) provided insights into the mechanics of reverse mortgage loans, including associated costs such as interest, closing fees, mortgage insurance premiums, and servicing charges. The study warned that the product might become expensive if the borrower passes away or relocates shortly after availing the loan, due to high upfront costs.

Venkatraman and Mishra (2013) offered a comprehensive understanding of the RML structure in India. They examined the products offered by various banks and discussed the challenges impeding the scheme's popularity despite its potential benefits.

Nakajima and Telyukova (2014) used a calibrated life-cycle model to assess the welfare benefits of reverse mortgage loans. Their findings indicated that low-income households with poor health conditions derived the greatest advantage from reverse mortgages, aligning with observed real-world patterns.

Kumar, Divakaruni, and Madhukar (2008) focused on the design of reverse mortgage products and assessed associated risks from the lender's viewpoint. They proposed that market surveys across metropolitan, urban, and semi-urban areas would be helpful in identifying suitable target segments and enhancing product marketability.

Srinivasan (2008) analyzed reverse mortgages from economic and social viewpoints, emphasizing the pros and cons, including tax implications. The study stressed the need

for product innovation and design improvements to increase the scheme's appeal among retirees.

Ameesha Nagar and N. Mahesh (2017) examined the emotional and financial attachments people have with their homes and the reluctance many Indians show toward monetizing their property. Despite low adoption in India compared to developed nations, the study suggested reverse mortgages are likely to gain traction, especially among individuals over 40 who view it as a useful tool for post-retirement planning.

Gireesh Chandra Tripathi and Chandrashekhar Iyer reviewed the broader RML environment in India, noting the lack of social security systems and the rise in elderly population. They emphasized the importance of understanding both the opportunities and implementation challenges of reverse mortgages to ensure informed policy decisions.

In another study by Ameesha Nagar and Mahesh, the authors analyzed India's mortgage market evolution, highlighting the role of reverse mortgages in helping seniors access housing equity without selling their property. They assessed the product's benefits and eligibility criteria and evaluated its potential impact on the housing and financial markets.

Chiang and Tsai (year not provided) presented a utility-based decision model that considered factors such as bequest motivation, retirement income, house price volatility, and interest rates. Their findings showed that seniors are more inclined to participate in reverse mortgage schemes when the principal limit is high, and the perceived cost is low.

Shruti Ashok and Deepika Dhingra (2020) conducted a case study analyzing two real-life scenarios to showcase how reverse mortgages can support financial independence in old age. One case illustrated how an individual maintained autonomy through the scheme, while another highlighted the struggles of relying solely on family support despite owning a home.

Finally, broader demographic projections indicate significant potential for reverse mortgages in India, particularly in urban areas like Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Goa, Chandigarh, and metropolitan centers. However, studies also point out a critical need for improved data infrastructure and product customization to suit regional needs and socioeconomic diversity.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine the Perception of respondents towards reverse mortgage in India with special reference to Bengaluru City.
2. To analyse the challenges faced by reverse mortgage products and to study the opportunities of reverse mortgage in India.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study uses both primary and secondary data for analysis, following an empirical research methodology. While secondary data was obtained from published

articles, magazines, books, theses, and scholarly journals, primary data was collected directly from Bengaluru city's citizens and secondary data was obtained from the official websites of banking organizations like the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and National Housing Bank (NHB). For collecting primary data, the study employed the convenience sampling technique, which involves selecting participants who are easily accessible to the researcher. The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula, which is especially suitable when dealing with large populations. The details of the sample size calculation are provided below.

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times \hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{\epsilon^2}$$
$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.5(1-0.5)}{0.05^2} = 384.16$$

e: desired level of precision, the margin of error

p: the fraction of the population (as percentage) that displays the attribute

z: the z-value, extracted from a z-table.

Universal sample size is considered to be 385 from the following equations.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Factor Analysis

To achieve the first objective that is to analyse the perception of respondents towards reverse mortgage factor analysis is performed. Factor analysis is data reduction tool used to reduce variables in order to understand the perception of respondents.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.724
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	751.874
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

KMO=.724 which is greater than 0.6, which indicate that all variables are significantly correlated. Hence, it is appropriate to carry out factor analysis. Variables with less than 0.4 as communality are not going to significantly contribute to the entire data. Hence, we discard such variables. Here the table of communalities is provided below in which all the variables have communality value more than 0.4. Hence, we consider all variables.

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total
1	2.798	13.988	13.988	2.798	13.988	13.988	1.966
2	2.062	10.312	24.300	2.062	10.312	24.300	1.673
3	1.345	6.725	31.025	1.345	6.725	31.025	1.976
4	1.166	5.830	36.855	1.166	5.830	36.855	1.370
5	1.053	5.264	42.119	1.053	5.264	42.119	1.531
6	1.030	5.152	47.271	1.030	5.152	47.271	1.829
7	.993	4.965	52.236				
8	.975	4.874	57.110				
9	.920	4.600	61.710				
10	.865	4.325	66.035				
11	.840	4.200	70.235				
12	.790	3.950	74.185				
13	.780	3.899	78.083				
14	.739	3.697	81.781				
15	.703	3.515	85.295				
16	.648	3.242	88.538				
17	.620	3.101	91.639				
18	.577	2.883	94.522				
19	.556	2.779	97.301				
20	.540	2.699	100.000				

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

To find the new factors and the variables associated with them

		Components					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Empowering Independent Senior Living	High potential of reverse mortgage in India.	.639					
	Interested in purchasing reverse mortgage	.718					
	Helps the senior citizen to stay independently	.638					
Limited Suitability Inheritance Impact	It is not suitable for Indian market		.612				
	Reduce the inheritance			.663			
	Lack of information about reverse mortgage				.614		
Awareness Gap	Banks have not done enough in marketing reverse mortgage to the public				.664		

Retirement Solution	Reverse mortgage provides a solution to financial problem senior citizen						.731	
	Disinterest in opting for reverse mortgage loan would be because you don't want to mortgage your own property							.686
Property Attachment	Disinterest in opting for reverse mortgage loan would be because you have other source of income							.689

The number of factors to be chosen is based on the Eigen values of the factors (>1) and the total variance explained by such factors (>60%). In the present case, we take 6 factors for further analysis since they have Eigen values>1 and total variance explained is 47.271.

Thus, the latent variable brought out by factor analysis are:

- 1. Empowering Independent Senior Living-** This factor focuses on the potential of reverse mortgage as a tool that allows senior citizens to live independently, providing them with the financial means to stay in their homes. It highlights the importance of financial security in older age, enabling seniors to maintain their autonomy without worrying about monthly expenses.
- 2. Limited Suitability-** This factor underscores the idea that reverse mortgage may not be a one-size-fits-all solution, particularly in the Indian market. There are concerns about its long-term viability, with some individuals perceiving it as unsuitable for cultural or market-specific reasons.
- 3. Inheritance Impact-** This component answers questions regarding the potential impact of reverse mortgages on heirs' inheritances. Seniors' desired legacy may be diminished if the home's worth is depleted by growing mortgage rates.
- 4. Awareness Gap-** This element emphasizes how little knowledge and information there is about reverse mortgages in the Indian market. Seniors' capacity to make wise judgments may be hampered by their incomplete understanding of the product and its advantages.
- 5. Retirement Solution-** This element highlights the function of reverse mortgages as a financial remedy for elderly people who are experiencing financial difficulties in their retirement. It offers a reverse mortgage as a means of meeting financial obligations without having to sell the house.
- 6. Property Attachment-** This element relates to some seniors' practical and emotional hesitancy to mortgage their homes, which may be their most valuable possession and a

source of pride. Furthermore, some elderly people may feel that they don't need to employ reverse mortgages because they have other sources of income.

Exploring the challenges and opportunities of the Reverse Mortgage in India

Opportunities and challenges are determined by the thematic analysis. Senior citizens can receive financial aid through reverse mortgage products, but there are still many obstacles to overcome. The potential and difficulties are identified for further analysis.

Challenges to Reverse Mortgage Adoption in India

1. Cultural and Emotional Attachment to Property

Homeownership is highly regarded in Indian society as a source of emotional and cultural significance in addition to being a financial asset. Many elderly people view their homes as symbols of security and legacy in addition to being places to live. Even if it means improving their retirement financial status, people find it difficult to contemplate the possibility of mortgaging their home because of this emotional attachment.

2. Lack of Awareness and Understanding

Lack of knowledge and comprehension of reverse mortgages is one of the main obstacles to their implementation in India. The hazards, possible advantages, and operation of reverse mortgages are unfamiliar to many seniors. Many people are reluctant to think of reverse mortgages as a feasible alternative if they are not properly educated. There is a knowledge gap since banks and financial institutions have not yet successfully promoted and informed the public about reverse mortgages.

3. Concerns About Inheritance

The possible effects on inheritance are a major worry for prospective reverse mortgage clients. For many families in India, transferring property to the following generation is a typical objective.

The wealth that elderly people want to leave for their successors may be diminished by reverse mortgages, which gradually lower the property's worth. Choosing a reverse mortgage is frequently hesitant due to this worry about undermining their heritage.

4. Complexity of the Product

Seniors may find it challenging to understand the many processes and intricate legal jargon involved in the reverse mortgage process. Furthermore, there is sometimes a lack of clarity in the terms and circumstances of reverse mortgages, which causes misunderstandings and erodes consumer confidence in the product.

Some of these problems might be resolved by streamlining the application procedure and increasing the clarity of the terms.

5. High Interest Rates and Financial Uncertainty

Reverse mortgages' growing interest rates may serve as a disincentive. These expenses have the potential to mount up over time, severely lowering the property's total value and deterring seniors who are worried about their home's value declining. Furthermore, many people are reluctant to assume the additional risk that comes with variable interest rates.

6. Cultural and Emotional Attachment to Property

Home ownership is frequently seen as the ultimate symbol of financial security and achievement in Indian culture. Many elders view their home as a sign of social position, family history, and pride in addition to being an asset. Seniors may find it difficult to contemplate mortgages, even if they provide financial relief, due to their emotional attachment to their homes.

This hesitancy is exacerbated by the conventional belief that owning property is an important aspect of their legacy, which they wish to leave to their descendants.

As a result, there is frequently opposition to the concept of employing a reverse mortgage, which necessitates giving up ownership rights.

Prospects for Future Expansion and Acceptance

Reverse mortgages have a lot of potential for growth and acceptance in India, despite the obstacles. There are a number of reasons why this financial instrument might gain broader acceptance in the future:

1. Growing Awareness and Financial Literacy

Reverse mortgages have a higher chance of becoming popular in India as financial literacy, especially among the elderly, continues to rise. The significance of educating the public about reverse mortgages is beginning to be recognized by banks and other financial organizations. Seniors could make better decisions and close the knowledge gap with targeted awareness campaigns, workshops, and instructional materials.

2. Government and Policy Support

The expansion of reverse mortgages might be greatly aided by the Indian government. More seniors may look into reverse mortgages as a way to secure their financial future if incentives are offered, such as tax benefits or advantageous policies. Regulations that shield elderly people from unscrupulous tactics may help increase trust in this product.

3. Changing Attitudes Toward Aging and Retirement

Alternative retirement income sources are becoming more and more necessary as the Indian population ages and more people abandon traditional family support systems. A potential for reverse mortgages to play a bigger part in retirement planning arises from this change in perspective, when seniors may no longer rely entirely on family for financial support. In order to alter perceptions of the product, banks and other financial institutions

should present reverse mortgages as a means of guaranteeing financial stability in old life.

4. Customization of Products

Reverse mortgages could be modified to better meet the requirements of senior citizens in India in order to boost adoption. Offering goods that enable seniors to receive periodic payments or lump sum payments based on their individual financial circumstances, for instance, could increase the product's appeal. Some of the main issues might also be resolved by creating reverse mortgage plans that provide better interest rate structures or safeguard inheritance.

5. Increasing Property Values

Seniors wishing to access their home equity may find reverse mortgages increasingly alluring as property values continue to climb in many Indian cities. Seniors may access larger sums of money without having to worry about losing their homes or their financial security as property values increased.

6. Partnerships with Senior Care Institutions

Reverse mortgages may be promoted through partnerships between banks, financial institutions, and senior care providers. Reverse mortgages, for example, can be promoted as a way to help seniors keep an independent lifestyle while making sure their financial needs are satisfied through collaborations with retirement communities or senior citizen associations.

7. Increasing Financial Literacy and Awareness Campaigns

Senior citizens in India are learning more about financial services and products as financial literacy initiatives continue to develop. Banks and other financial organizations might respond by launching more focused awareness efforts about reverse mortgages, including its advantages, disadvantages, and workings. The awareness gap can be closed through cooperation with senior citizen organizations, educational programs, and internet resources. Seniors may be more likely to choose reverse mortgages if they are informed about how they can offer a stable source of income in their later years.

8. Shifting Demographics and Family Structures

Reverse mortgages are made possible by India's shifting demographics, which are marked by an aging population and changing family arrangements. The demand for financial independence in retirement grows as more families become nuclear and seniors live alone or with little family support. For seniors who are no longer able to access a pension or a reliable source of income, reverse mortgages may be a viable option. Furthermore, many seniors are finding it challenging to live comfortably on their meager resources due to urbanization and rising living expenses. This problem can be solved with reverse mortgages, which turn home equity into a steady source of income.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, even though reverse mortgages provide senior individuals in India with substantial financial advantages, there are a number of obstacles preventing their widespread use. Reluctance is influenced by a variety of factors, including cultural attachment to property, ignorance, inheritance worries, product complexity, high interest rates, and restricted availability. Nonetheless, there are chances for improvement through older education, product simplification, and the provision of more adaptable choices. Reverse mortgages have the potential to be a crucial instrument for giving India's older population financial stability and independence with increased government and financial institution awareness and assistance.

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Links

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